

Knowledge, Attitude and Awareness of COVID-19 Infection among Osun State University Community – An Online Survey

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Background information: Covid-19 infection was declared pandemic by World health Organization on March 11, 2021 in recognition of the widespread global transmission. Compliance with appropriate preventive and control policies instituted by Nigeria Government towards limiting the spread of infection is influenced by Knowledge and attitude among community members. The objective of this study was to determine the knowledge level, attitude and practices towards COVID 19 infection among teaching, non-teaching and students within Osun-State University community.

Methods

Study design: The study utilized a descriptive cross-sectional design done between months of April and May, 2020

Study setting: This study was carried out in Osun State University. The University is a tertiary institution with 6 campuses located in Oshogbo, Ejigbo, Ifetedo, Ikire, Ipetu-Ijesha, and Okuku.

Sample size calculation: This was determined using Leslie fisher formula.

Instrument of data collection: The study was utilized an electronic web-based questionnaire designed with the use of Google form to elicit responses from willing participants.

Data Collection and Analysis: Data was analysed using IBM SPSS (23). Descriptive and inferential statistics analysis was used to describe items included in the survey. All results from the field were coded, compiled and properly recorded in a pass word protected excel spread sheet, made only accessible to the research team.

Ethical consideration: A written approval was obtained from the Ethics and research Committee of the College of Health Sciences, Osun State University, Osogbo. The researchers were guided by the principles for ethical research as stated in the Declaration of Helsinki

Result

According to socio-demographic status, age ranges from 16-64 years with mean of 29.2 + 17.4 years. Majority of respondents i.e 237 (64.4%) are within 17-26 years, Yoruba

358 (97.3%), Christian 257(69.8%) students 245 (66.6%), married 118(32.1%) and with tertiary educational status 350 (95.1%) –

Regarding attitude towards corona virus, 309(84%) disagreed that corona virus cannot affect black people while 311(84.5%) agreed to maintain social distance even if family member appear at the door step. Also, majority 277(75.3%) disagree that it is embarrassing to use face mask when going out while 135(36.7%) believed that Covid 19 virus is a conspiracy theory. Only 10 (2.7%) agreed Corona virus is not real while 309(84%) admits it is real

Regarding preventive practices, 278(75,5%), 66(17.9%) and 89(24.2%) always wash their hands, use hand gloves and nose mask while 147 (39.9%) , 350(95.1%) and 331 (89.9%) never receive visitors, exposed to people with symptoms of corona virus as well as travel during the pandemic period

Table: Summarized knowledge, attitude and Preventive Practices

Variable	Frequency	Percentages
Summarized knowledge		
Good knowledge	248	67.4
poor knowledge	120	32.6
Summarized attitude		
good attitude	240	65.2
Poor attitude	128	34.8
Summarized Preventive Practices		
Good practice	160	43.5
Poor practice	208	56.5

Discussion

In this study, more than half of the respondents (67.4%) had correct knowledge on COVID 19 infection. Even though there were variations across different age groups, higher percentages of 80.5% and 90% were reported in previous studies done in Malaysia and China among community residents though differences in scoring and categorization of knowledge scores by the authors of these manuscripts makes comparison difficult across board. (Azlan et al 2020,) (Zhong, 2020)

Concerning attitude, more than two third of respondents held an optimistic attitude towards COVID-19; almost all the respondents -84% admits infection is real

while another 75.3% belief in using face mask as means of curbing the spread of infection when leaving their homes. Such high level of positive attitude were reported among study populations in China (Zhong, 2020)

Majority of the participants in this present study took precautions such as practising hand hygiene always (75.5%), avoiding travelling to places (89.9%) in line with directives from Government towards curbing the spread of infection. in line with infection control guideline circulated by Centre for disease control

Conclusion

Respondents within Osun State University

demonstrated high knowledge and good attitude but poor preventive practices towards corona virus infection. There is need for periodic health promotional campaigns to address such deficiencies

Keywords: Corona virus, Knowledge, Attitude, Preventive Practices

Disclosure: None

References

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